

Recent Advances in RF Tomography for Underground Imaging

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Abstract— **Underground imaging for tunnel detection is proposed using the principles of radio frequency (RF) tomography. In RF tomography, a set of distributed transmitters and receivers are deployed arbitrarily above the ground, or slightly buried. These transmitters radiate suitable narrowband, low-frequency waveforms into the ground. The resulting wavefront impinges upon underground objects, scattering electromagnetic energy in all directions. Receivers sample the scattered signal, mitigate direct-path leakage, retrieve the phasor of the scattered signals, and relay this information to a base station. After adaptive processing of measured data, an image of the underground facilities is achieved.**

RF Tomography; Tunnel Detection;

I. INTRODUCTION

Tunnel and underground facility (UGF) detection is critical for both military and civilian governing bodies, especially for national security, monitoring criminal activities, border control, concealed weapon detection, search and rescue, etc. Several techniques have been proposed, but few are applicable in dangerous, unfriendly or inaccessible places. Such techniques must need minimal human intervention, should have minimal impact of the ground, perform remote and close-in sensing, and be affordable. The use of RF tomography can potentially solve many of these requirements, thus making underground imaging an easily deployable technology. The underlying principles and mathematical background of RF tomography have been introduced, derived and inspired by many earlier works [1-8], though the idea of using distributed sensors for underground imaging was pioneered by Wicks [9] and a first comprehensive mathematical description was given by the authors in [10].

Radio Frequency (RF) Tomography is a theory for the imaging of high-contrast dielectric / conducting extended targets embedded in highly attenuated, highly cluttered, complex environments, when an arbitrarily *distributed* network of RF sensors is employed. For underground imaging, a set of low-cost, configurable, automated, narrowband electromagnetic transmitter/receivers (named *transponders*) are placed on top, above, or shallowly buried in the ground at *arbitrary* positions. In a preliminary stage, sensors accurately identify their position, orientation and time reference using GPS technology or digital compass. Once the calibration phase is concluded, a predetermined set of transmitters radiates a known waveform using a suitable polarization. The probing wave impinges upon a dielectric / conducting anomaly (representing the target), thus arising a scattered

wave-field. The distributed receivers collect samples of the electric field, remove noise, clutter and the direct path, and store the information concerning only the scattered field. In the next iteration, a different set of transmitters is activated, or different waveforms / polarizations are used. Subsequently, the collected data is relayed to the command and control post for processing and imaging, e.g. an overlying base station, or an unmanned aerial vehicle (see [10] for a pictorial representation). The system operates using ultra-narrowband, adaptive waveforms, thus ensuring low noise, low dispersion and affordable cost.

The basic mathematical background of RF tomography for belowground imaging has been introduced in [10-12]. In this work, we present the most recent advances in RF tomography developed by our group, since the publication of the first article [10]. These improvements address some of the practical challenges facing RF tomography.

II. TRANSMITTERS AND RECEIVERS

A. Rationale and Notation

In order to exploit the full potential of geometric diversity, RF tomography requires a network of “smart” sensors able to (i) steer radiation nulls along arbitrary directions (e.g., to overcome challenges due to direct illumination between Tx and Rx pairs), and (ii) polarization diversity [10]. To achieve these capabilities, one needs to devise sensors that are able to control different channels with different driving currents. For example, one can devise a sensor constructed using two crossed dipoles fed separately: by properly changing amplitude and phase of the driving currents, one can create any polarization state, or one can steer the radiation pattern nulls to any desired direction in a plane. The actual realization of co-located elementary dipoles is a hard task, mainly due to poor radiation efficiency, non-ideal current distribution, to the proximity of the air-ground interface, and to mutual coupling between different channels. These factors lead to different radiation patterns that need to be properly accounted for in the development of a forward model.

We assume that there are N transmitters located at the surface or slightly underground, each one at position \mathbf{r}_n^a . Each transmitter consists of C channels (usually, $C = 2, 3$), which are separately fed by driving currents at a fixed angular frequency ω , which can be expressed by a complex-valued phasor $d_{n,c}$. We also assume that M receiving sensors are

deployed above or in the ground. The m -th receiver is located at position \mathbf{r}_m^b and oriented along the unit-norm direction $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_m$. Differently from transmitters, receivers are assumed to be electrically small dipoles oriented along $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_m$, i.e. they measure the projection of the electric field at position \mathbf{r}_m^b onto the vector $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_m$. Transmitters and receivers do not need to be co-located. We will limit our theory for the single frequency case, but these derivations can be easily extended to the multi-frequency case.

For simplicity, we assume that transmitters can be modeled as linear (wire) antennas, such as finite length dipoles, loops, beverage antennas, dipole arrays, log-periodic antennas, helix antennas, etc. so that the radiated field can be evaluated as superposition of the ones given by linear elements (subdivisions) of the antenna in the space.

B. Equivalent Green's Function

Since we assume that transmitters are not infinitesimally small, we need to determine the effects to the radiation pattern of the actual current distribution in space. Clearly, when a driving current is applied to the c -th input terminal of the n -th linear antenna, a current distribution is induced on its wireframe. We assume known the induced current distribution due to an excitation $d_{n,c} = 1\text{A}$; in fact, this quantity can be generally computed analytically or using MoM solvers. This current distribution in space is divided in P small dipoles, each one centered at $\mathbf{r}_{n,c}^p$, having length l , with a relative current amplitude $I_{n,c}^p$ and phase $\varphi_{n,c}^p$, and a moment direction defined by the unit-norm vector $\hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,c}^p$. According to this notation, the segment p of the current distribution in the space due to the driving current $d_{n,c}$ is located at position:

$$\mathbf{r}_{n,c}^p = \mathbf{r}_n^a + \mathbf{r}_{n,c}^p \quad (1)$$

and carries a current

$$\mathbf{a}_{n,c,p} = d_{n,c} I_{n,c}^p \exp(j\varphi_{n,c}^p) \hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,c}^p \quad (2)$$

Let us assume that the n -th transmitter is using simultaneously all C channels, each one driven by the current $d_{n,c}$. Using (1) and (2), the electric field at a generic position \mathbf{r} due to the n -th Tx can be written using the superposition principle as

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{c=1}^C \sum_{p=1}^P j\omega\mu_0 l \underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_{n,c}^p) \cdot \mathbf{a}_{n,c}^p \quad (3)$$

where $\underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ is the dyadic Green's function of the problem. The numerical computation of $\underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ is discussed in Section III. Eq. (3) can be expressed in a more

compact and elegant form by defining an *equivalent Green's function*:

$$\underline{\mathbf{G}}_{eq}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_n^a) = \sum_{p=1}^P l \begin{bmatrix} \left[\underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_{n,1}^p) \cdot \mathbf{a}_{n,1}^p \right]^T \\ \left[\underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_{n,c}^p) \cdot \mathbf{a}_{n,c}^p \right]^T \\ \vdots \\ \left[\underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_{n,C}^p) \cdot \mathbf{a}_{n,C}^p \right]^T \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (4)$$

By collecting the C driving currents $d_{n,c}$ in a column vector:

$$\mathbf{d}_n = [d_{n,1} \quad d_{n,c} \quad \cdots \quad d_{n,C}]^T \quad (5)$$

Eq. (3) can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}) = j\omega\mu_0 \underline{\mathbf{G}}_{eq}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_n^a) \cdot \mathbf{d}_n \quad (6)$$

Note the similarities between $\underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ and $\underline{\mathbf{G}}_{eq}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$: While the classical Green's function accounts for the field radiated at \mathbf{r} by an elementary source at \mathbf{r}' , the equivalent Green's function connects a multi-dimensional *driving current* source at \mathbf{r}' with the electric field at \mathbf{r} . Hence, while the classical Green's function can be considered the spatial impulse response of the scene, the equivalent Green's function depends on the choice of the antenna, and can be interpreted as the spatial "antenna response" of the scene. However, certain differences are notable; for example, the equivalent Green's function is generally a $3 \times C$ matrix, and it is not dimensionless. Nevertheless, its definition will be extremely useful to simplify the forward model for RF tomography, as well as to define suitable signal processing.

C. Canonical Examples

We will derive the mathematical expression of the equivalent Green's function for some canonical cases. Let us assume that our sensor is composed of three co-located and orthogonal dipoles (i.e., *vector sensor*), each one of length l and oriented along the direction $\hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,c}$ (note that $\hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,1} \perp \hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,2} \perp \hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,3}$), that are electrically small (i.e. $\lambda \gg l$). In this case, the driving current vector \mathbf{d}_n is made of 3 elements, and the equivalent Green's function becomes simply:

$$\underline{\mathbf{G}}_{eq}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_n^a) = l \begin{bmatrix} \left[\underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_n^a) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,1} \right]^T \\ \left[\underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_n^a) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,2} \right]^T \\ \left[\underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_n^a) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,3} \right]^T \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (7)$$

Eq. (7) is generally valid when frequencies are in the lower range of HF, and it will be used in the simulations presented in this work.

Another canonical case is to consider a vector sensor located in a homogeneous space but having size comparable with the wavelength, i.e. a sinusoidal current distribution. In this case each orthogonal dipole of the vector sensor, oriented along the direction $\hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,c}$ (with $\hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,1} \perp \hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,2} \perp \hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,3}$), has length L , and is partitioned in P segments, each one of length l :

$$l = L/P \quad (8)$$

The position of a partition p of each orthogonal dipole can be expressed using the following vectors:

$$\mathbf{r}_{n,c}^p = \mathbf{r}_n^a + (p - P/2 - 1/2) \hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,c} \quad p = 1 \dots P \quad (9)$$

And the current distributions is

$$\mathbf{a}_{n,c}^p \cong l \sin \left\{ k_D \left[L/2 - |l(p - P/2 - 1/2)| \right] \right\} \hat{\mathbf{i}}_{n,c} \quad (10)$$

where k_D is the wavenumber in the homogeneous medium.

Substituting (9) and (10) in (4) one can obtain the equivalent Green's function for finite length vector sensors. The discretization does not need to be fine: in general, we noted that $P = 4$ provides satisfactory results.

III. IRREGULAR TERRAIN

The dyadic Green's function $\underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ is strongly dependent on the scene in which sensors and targets are located. When the air-earth interface is flat, analytical formulations of $\underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ are available [1,5-6,11]. However, in many cases the terrain is generally not flat with respect to the operating frequencies; therefore, the proper Green's function of the problem cannot be computed analytically, and must be calculated numerically. Here, we use a numerical method to compute numerical Green's functions that is discussed in details in [13]. Basically, we compute the numerical Green's function starting from the assumption of a flat interface, and then adding the contribution of voxels representing dunes or hills, using a method of moment approach. The air half-space is modeled as free-space medium, while the ground half-space is modeled as a homogeneous medium with background relative dielectric permittivity ϵ_D , background conductivity σ_D , and magnetic permeability μ_0 . The dielectric/conducting targets are assumed to reside in a pre-determined investigation domain D . For a generic observation point in D located at \mathbf{r} , and a current source located at \mathbf{r}' , the numerical Green's function for the irregular terrain can be approximated as follows:

$$\underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = \underline{\mathbf{G}}_h(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') + \sum_{k=1}^K \underline{\mathbf{G}}_S(\mathbf{r}_k, \mathbf{r}') \mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{r}) \quad (11)$$

where $\underline{\mathbf{G}}_h(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ is the Green's dyad for the half-space with planar interface and the $\underline{\mathbf{G}}_S(\mathbf{r}_k, \mathbf{r}')$ represent the

contribution due to a perturbation of the surface located at a voxel \mathbf{r}_k (whose position is assumed known). The $\underline{\mathbf{G}}_S(\mathbf{r}_k, \mathbf{r}')$ are computed by solving the following matrix equation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 - \mathbf{C}_1 & -\mathbf{C}_k & -\mathbf{C}_K \\ -\mathbf{C}_k & \ddots & \\ -\mathbf{C}_K & & 1 - \mathbf{C}_K \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{G}}_S(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}') \\ \vdots \\ \underline{\mathbf{G}}_S(\mathbf{r}_K, \mathbf{r}') \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{G}}_I(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}') \\ \vdots \\ \underline{\mathbf{G}}_I(\mathbf{r}_K, \mathbf{r}') \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where

$$\mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{r}) = \int_{D_k} \underline{\mathbf{G}}_h(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'') k_h^2(z'') V_t(\mathbf{r}'') d\mathbf{r}'' \quad (13)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{G}}_I(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = \int_R \underline{\mathbf{G}}_h(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'') \underline{\mathbf{G}}_h(\mathbf{r}'', \mathbf{r}') k_h^2(z'') V_t(\mathbf{r}'') d\mathbf{r}'' \quad (14)$$

D_k is the volume of the k -th voxel, R is the support of V_t , $k_h^2(z'')$ is the wavenumber assuming flat surface, and $V_t(\mathbf{r}'')$ is a function accounting for the deviation from a flat surface case, i.e.:

$$V_t(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} \epsilon_D + j\sigma_D / (\omega\epsilon_0) - 1 & \{z > 0, \mathbf{r} \in \text{earth}\} \\ \left[\epsilon_D + j\sigma_D / (\omega\epsilon_0) \right]^{-1} - 1 & \{z < 0, \mathbf{r} \in \text{air}\} \\ 0 & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

IV. DYADIC CONTRAST FUNCTION

The objective of RF tomography for underground imaging is to localize, identify and gain information about the geometry of the buried scattering anomalies. In order to satisfy these needs, we suppose that a scattering phenomenon (i.e. an equivalent current source) occurring at a position \mathbf{r}' inside D is due mainly to three causes: a deviation in the relative dielectric permittivity $\epsilon_r(\mathbf{r}')$ from the background, a deviation in the conductivity $\sigma(\mathbf{r}')$ from the background, and a depolarization effect due to the presence of a dipole moment distribution. The last contribution can be represented as follow: the dipole moment $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{r}')$ of an electrically small metallic wire embedded in the background medium, whose length and position are represented by the vector $\mathbf{t}(\mathbf{r}')$, generated by an electric field represented by the vector $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}')$ can be expressed as [16]:

$$\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{r}') = K \mathbf{t}(\mathbf{r}') \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}') \mathbf{t}(\mathbf{r}') / \|\mathbf{t}(\mathbf{r}')\| \quad (16)$$

where K is a proper constant that needs to be determined according to material properties, but is unnecessary for our purposes. Using simple vector algebra, eq. (16) can be represented in matrix form. Hence, the superposition of these three scattering effects can be formalized using a *dyadic contrast function* $\underline{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{r}')$, defined as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{r}') = K \begin{bmatrix} t_x^2 + V/K & t_x t_y & t_x t_z \\ t_x t_y & t_y^2 + V/K & t_y t_z \\ t_x t_z & t_y t_z & t_z^2 + V/K \end{bmatrix} (\mathbf{r}') \quad (17)$$

where

$$V(\mathbf{r}') = \varepsilon_r(\mathbf{r}') - \varepsilon_D + j(\sigma(\mathbf{r}') - \sigma_D) / 2\pi f \varepsilon_0 \quad (18)$$

is the usual contrast function [10]. When $\underline{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{r}')$ is determined, one can easily discriminate between dielectric, conducting and dipole scattering phenomena within the voxel under consideration.

Note that the introduction of a dyadic contrast function is dramatically increasing the number of unknowns of the problem. If the depolarization effect due to dipole scattering can be considered negligible, then the dyadic contrast function in (17) can be approximated with the scalar quantity (18). Due to computational limitations, in our simulations we will consider the scalar representation of the contrast function, expressed in (18).

Figure 1: Geometry for the forward model

V. LINEARIZED FORWARD MODEL

Following the derivations reported in [10-11], the contrast dyad $\underline{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{r}')$ can be related to the total (scalar) electric field collected by the m -th receiver, due to simultaneous transmission of s transmitters (identified by the index set Γ_S)

$$E(\mathbf{r}_m^b, \hat{\mathbf{b}}_m, \Gamma_S), \text{ via the relation:}$$

$$E(\mathbf{r}_m^b, \hat{\mathbf{b}}_m, \Gamma_S) = j\omega\mu_0 \left\{ \overbrace{\hat{\mathbf{b}}_m^T \cdot \left[\sum_{n \in \Gamma_S} \underline{\mathbf{G}}_{eq}(\mathbf{r}_m^b, \mathbf{r}_n^a) \cdot \mathbf{d}_n \right]}^{\text{Direct Path Contribution}} + \overbrace{k_0^2 \iiint_D \mathbf{b}_m^T \cdot \underline{\mathbf{G}}(\mathbf{r}_m^b, \mathbf{r}') \cdot \underline{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{r}') \cdot \left[\sum_{n \in \Gamma_S} \underline{\mathbf{G}}_{eq}(\mathbf{r}', \mathbf{r}_n^a) \cdot \mathbf{d}_n \right] d\mathbf{r}'}^{\text{Scattered Field from Targets}} \right. \\ \left. \overbrace{+ \hat{\mathbf{b}}_m^T \cdot \mathbf{Z}(\mathbf{r}_m^b, \hat{\mathbf{b}}_m, \Gamma_S)}^{\text{Noise, Errors, Non-Linear Terms}} \right\} \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{Z} represents an (unknown) error vector accounting for high-order Born series, clutter and noise. This approximated formula represents the *Forward Model* of RF Tomography in its simplest form.

VI. DISCRETIZATION

The continuous linear integral equation in (19) can be discretized using the method of moments. Therefore, we collect a discrete set of measurements by varying $\mathbf{r}_m^b, \hat{\mathbf{b}}_m, s, \omega$ to form a vector \mathbf{e} ; the effect of \mathbf{Z} is approximately accounted as a source noise. The domain D is discretized into k voxels, each one located at \mathbf{r}'_k , so that we can recast the dyadic function $\underline{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{r}')$ into a column vector \mathbf{v} . The second term in (19) (i.e. the linear integral operation on $\underline{\mathbf{V}}$) can be discretized in a matrix $\underline{\mathbf{L}}$, while the direct path contribution can be represented by a vector \mathbf{p} . Therefore, the forward model can be approximated in discrete form by $\mathbf{e} \cong \underline{\mathbf{L}} \cdot \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{p}$. In principle the estimation of \mathbf{v} can be performed as:

$$\mathbf{v} \cong \underline{\mathbf{L}}^{-1} \cdot (\mathbf{e} - \mathbf{p}) \quad (20)$$

this simple matrix representation represents the formulation of the *inverse* operation. Estimating \mathbf{v} is generally a hard task because 1) $\underline{\mathbf{L}}$ is heavily underdetermined, ill-conditioned and is itself affected by estimation errors, 2) \mathbf{e} is affected by noise, clutter, and nonlinearities, 3) The difference $\mathbf{e} - \mathbf{p}$ may be extremely low, since in most cases the direct path is 50-60 dB higher than the scattered field itself.

VII. DIRECT PATH MITIGATION

One way to mitigate the strong direct path coupling between Tx and Rx pairs has been proposed in [12], where one assumes to properly design the feeding currents \mathbf{d}_n for a set of N_S simultaneously activated transmitters in order to achieve minimum coupling at a determined location. To provide robustness to uncertainties, we seek current distributions that produce low coupling over a small area surrounding the m -th receiver. This task is accomplished by considering a suitable

set of Δ points in the neighbor of \mathbf{r}_m^b , each one positioned at a (small) distance $\delta\mathbf{r}^b$ from \mathbf{r}_m^b . Furthermore, the relative importance of each point is determined by a weight w_δ . The amount of the coupling effect at the receiver position \mathbf{r}_m^b and moment direction $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_m$, and in its surrounding Δ points $\delta\mathbf{r}^b$ can be quantified via the functional:

$$J = \left\| \sum_{n \in \Gamma_s} \sum_{\delta=1}^{\Delta} \hat{\mathbf{b}}_m \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}_m^b + \delta\mathbf{r}^b, \mathbf{r}_n^a) \right\|_2^2 \quad (21)$$

$$= \left\| \sum_{n \in \Gamma_s} \hat{\mathbf{b}}_m \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_l \cdot \mathbf{d}_l \right\|_2^2 = \sum_{n,l \in \Gamma_s} \mathbf{d}_n^H \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_n^H \cdot (\hat{\mathbf{b}}_m \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}}_m^T) \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_l \cdot \mathbf{d}_l$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{G}}_{n,l}(\mathbf{r}_m^b, \mathbf{r}_{n,l}^a) = \sum_{\delta=1}^{\Delta} w_\delta \mathbf{G}_{eq}(\mathbf{r}_m^b + \delta\mathbf{r}^b, \mathbf{r}_{n,l}^a) \quad (22)$$

The functional in (21) can be recast in matrix form:

$$J = \mathbf{d}^H \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{d} \quad (23)$$

where the positive semidefinite matrix \mathbf{K} is defined by

$$\mathbf{K} \square \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_1^H (\hat{\mathbf{b}}_m \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}}_m^T) \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_1 & \cdots & \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_1^H (\hat{\mathbf{b}}_m \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}}_m^T) \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_{N_s} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_{N_s}^H (\hat{\mathbf{b}}_m \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}}_m^T) \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_1 & \cdots & \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_{N_s}^H (\hat{\mathbf{b}}_m \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}}_m^T) \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_{N_s} \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

and \mathbf{d} represents all driving currents in the scene:

$$\mathbf{d} \square [\mathbf{d}_1^T \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{d}_{N_s}^T]^T \quad (25)$$

The optimal choice of the transmitters currents \mathbf{d}_{opt} is the vector that minimizes J . As such, we solve the constrained optimization problem given by

$$\mathbf{d}_{opt} = \arg \min [J(\mathbf{d})] \quad (26)$$

$$\text{subject to : } \|\mathbf{d}_n\|_2^2 = \mathbf{d}_n^H \cdot \mathbf{d}_n = 1 \quad \forall n \in \Gamma_s \quad (27)$$

This minimum coupling condition represents a non-convex set of constraints, and the minimization can be performed using standard techniques such as sequential quadratic programming, or interior point methods. Using this method, we guarantee that for each measurement set the vector \mathbf{p} is virtually reduced to zero, thus the measured field is predominantly the scattered field from targets.

VIII. INVERSION PROCEDURES

At this point, we assume that the direct-path vector \mathbf{p} in (20) has been properly mitigated. Therefore, one needs to perform an accurate matrix inversion that returns the best

approximation of \mathbf{v} in some metric. Among several methods that have been proposed [6], [10-12], [14], we believe that Truncated SVD and Sparse Minimization are good candidates.

A. Truncated SVD

An efficient way to invert the ill-conditioned matrix \mathbf{L} is to take advantage of Singular Value Decomposition (SVD). In fact, \mathbf{L} can be decomposed in its SVD representation as $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{\Pi}^H$, where \mathbf{S} is a diagonal matrix containing the ordered singular values s_i of \mathbf{L} . The pseudoinverse of \mathbf{L} can be written as:

$$\mathbf{L}^\dagger = \mathbf{\Pi} \mathbf{S}^{-1} \mathbf{\Lambda}^H \quad (28)$$

Singular values associated to \mathbf{S}^{-1} that are considerably large compared to $1/s_1$ represents the sensitive directions of \mathbf{L} : along these directions, small amounts of noise or clutter in the collected electric field will lead to a large (undesired) deviation of \mathbf{v} . A way to remove this sensitivity is to consider only the first q smaller singular values of \mathbf{S}^{-1} and setting to zero the remaining large ones. This strategy is commonly referred to as “Truncated SVD” [14]. Accordingly, the dielectric profile can be estimated as $\mathbf{v}(q) = \mathbf{\Pi} \mathbf{S}_q^{-1} \mathbf{\Lambda}^H$. This method is relatively accurate in any scenario and moderately resistant to noise interference.

B. Sparse Minimization

Frequently, it is desired that \mathbf{v} is sparse. A sparse solution dramatically reduces artifacts and improves the probability of detection and tracing of underground facilities. To achieve this goal, we seek \mathbf{v} as the solution of the following convex minimization problem:

$$\text{minimize } \|\mathbf{v}\|_1 \quad \text{subject to } \|\mathbf{e} - \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{v}\|_2 < \mathcal{G} \quad (29)$$

where \mathcal{G} needs to be opportunely selected. Among the vast literature regarding sparse minimization, we preferred to use the algorithm FISTA [17], due to its speed and simplicity of operation.

IX. SIMULATIONS

In this work, we present an FDTD simulation using GPRMAX [15] to prove the validity of RF tomography for tunnel detection. Two hollow cylinders of radius 1.5m simulating two tunnels are located at depth -15m belowground. Six co-located transmitters and receivers are deployed on the ground according to Fig 2. Tx and Rx are supposed to be crossed dipoles, and the radiating waveform is a stepped FM ranging from 2MHz to 6MHz, with frequency interval of 0.25MHz. At each step and each frequency, two different Tx are activated per time, and the proper phase and direction are chosen according to (26)-(27) in order to minimize the direct path at a particular Rx. Both DAC and ADC have a finite dynamic

range of 16 bits. Once the direct path is mitigated, the field is sampled in time domain and transformed in phasor form. This procedure is repeated for all measurement configurations, so that \mathbf{e} and \mathbf{L} can be filled (using the Green's function for the half space reported in [14]). Finally, the domain D is reconstructed using both TSVD and Sparse Minimization, and sliced at depth -15m: the contrast function is then plotted (see Fig.3).

Figure 2: Geometry of the simulation. Tunnels are at depth of -15m.

Figure 3: Reconstructed image using TSVD (left), and FISTA (right)

X. CONCLUSIONS

This work described the most recent advances in RF tomography for underground imaging. With respect to the first paper introducing RF tomography for tunnel detection [11], we proposed 1) a novel forward model formulation that includes the possibility of having multiple transmitters, each one having different channels fed separately; 2) the concept of equivalent Green's function to tackle radiators that are different from the ideal electrically small dipole. 3) The possibility to image irregular terrains; 4) The concept of using a dyadic contrast function, in order to retrieve some basic shape features of the buried target; 5) A novel direct-path mitigation strategy based upon simultaneous transmission of signals from different transmitters; 6) The use of compressive sensing algorithms to invert the matrix equation.

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